
THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN PARSING AND VERBAL MWE IDENTIFICATION: IT'S COMPLICATED

TECHNICAL REPORT

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March 11, 2026

ABSTRACT

It is commonly assumed that verbal multiword expression (VMWE) identification and syntactic parsing can mutually benefit from one another, motivating a wide range of joint and syntax-aware approaches. In this paper, we systematically re-examine this assumption and show that the relationship between parsing and VMWE identification is far from straightforward. Using gold-standard dependency and VMWE annotations from French PARSEME 1.2 and English STREUSLE, we evaluate multiple ways of incorporating syntactic information into neural VMWE identification models. These include multi-task learning with shared representations, uncertainty-based dynamic loss weighting, supervised contrastive learning over dependency relations, and explicit dependency-relation embeddings concatenated to contextualized token representations. While dynamic loss weighting improves over naive multi-task training, none of the joint or syntax-enhanced approaches consistently outperform a strong MWE-only baseline. In several settings, syntactic supervision substantially degrades performance and leads to unstable training behavior. Our results suggest that, despite strong theoretical motivation, current neural models struggle to exploit explicit syntactic information for VMWE identification, and that simpler task-specific architectures remain more effective.

Keywords verbal multiword expressions, MWE identification, dependency parsing, multi-task learning, neural NLP

1 Introduction

Multiword expressions (MWEs) are combinations of at least two lexemes that exhibit semantic, lexical, syntactic, pragmatic or statistical idiomaticity (Baldwin and Kim, 2010). For example, the meaning of the infamous idiom *kick the bucket* ('to die') is not a sum of its parts but something completely unrelated to the meaning of the components. In such a case we talk about semantic idiomaticity. The same goes for *by and large* ('generally speaking'), but on top of that it is also syntactically idiosyncratic in that it is an illegal coordination of a preposition and an adjective. We can add one more type of idiomaticity with *ad hoc* which is also lexically idiomatic because the English dictionary does not contain the word *ad* or *hoc*.¹ All of these expressions are statistically idiomatic as well because they occur more often

¹For this reason *ad hoc* is also syntactically and semantically idiomatic "because there is no lexical knowledge associated directly with the parts from which to predict the behaviour of the MWE." (Baldwin and Kim, 2010)

together than chance would allow it. Last but not least, something like *all aboard* is pragmatically idiomatic since it is associated with a fixed set of situations.

However, we are only interested in a subset of MWEs, and that is verbal MWEs (VMWEs). VMWEs have especially challenging properties like discontinuity or overlap. According to the PARSEME annotation guidelines, VMWEs are just MWEs “whose syntactic head in the prototypical form is a verb”². Furthermore, PARSEME classifies VMWEs into the following categories:

- Light-verb constructions (LVCs)
- Verbal Idioms (VIDs)
- Inherently reflexive verbs (IRVs)
- Verb-particle constructions (VPCs)
- Multi-verb constructions (MVCs)
- Inherently adpositional verbs (IAVs)

Now, it has long been recognized that MWEs are a bottleneck for some NLP applications (Sag et al., 2002) and that there is a need to automatically identify them should they occur in a text. E.g. parsing³ would be an application that could benefit from identifying MWEs. It would reduce the search space if a parser knew beforehand that *by and large* functions as a unit. Vice versa, the identification of MWEs could benefit from syntactic information yielded by a parser. That is why it is not unreasonable to assume a joint approach, i.e. parsing and identification at the same time, is the way to go. There are two possibilities for a joint approach which have both advantages and drawbacks. The first approach is to incorporate the identification into the parsing itself, for example by using a standard parser and changing the arcs between MWE components with MWE-specific labels. Figure 1 shows how that would look like. The verbal idiom (VID) *spill the beans* (‘to reveal a secret’) is a syntactically regular combination of a verb and an object which is reflected by the annotation in Figure 1 (a). In Figure 1 (b) on the other hand, we can see that the regular arc labels were replaced by MWE-specific ones (VID) to indicate that *spilled the beans* is an instance of a MWE.

(a) Standard annotation.

(b) MWE-specific annotation.

Figure 1: MWE identification and parsing.

One obvious limitation of this approach is the handling of single-token MWEs:

- (1) **Schmink** dir das mal **ab**.
Wipe to yourself that once off.
‘Forget about that/That is not going to happen.’
- (2) Das kannst du dir **abschminken**.
That can you to yourself wipe off.
‘Forget about that/That is not going to happen.’

The verb and the particle of the German verb-particle construction *abschminken* (literal: wipe off (make-up), idiomatic: ‘to give up on something’) can also be written as one word and accordingly there are no arcs for the parser to predict.

²https://parseme.fr/lis-lab.fr/parseme-st-guidelines/1.2/?page=010_Definitions_and_scope/020_Verbal_multiword_expressions

³We will exclusively deal with dependency parsing in this paper, even if not explicitly stated.

To counter this problem Simkó et al. (2017) train a POS tagger on top of a parser to account for single-token MWEs. Another remedy would be to also parse subwords, but to our knowledge there has not been such an approach to MWEs. The second approach is to model the task as a multi-task problem with two (or three⁴) different losses which we minimize during training:

$$loss = loss_{MWE} + loss_{dep} \quad (1)$$

Here, $loss_{MWE}$ is the cross-entropy loss for assigning each token a BIO label for MWE identification. $loss_{dep}$ is the loss for dependency parsing.

Now the question is, is there any evidence for the assumption that a joint approach is beneficial to MWE identification? The issue regarding the first approach is that usually, the authors do not compare their results to approaches that perform MWE identification only. For the multi-task approach, at least Taslimipour et al. (2020) report numbers for the multi-task setting and identification only which enables us to compare results. Their system consists of a linear layer on top of BERT and a tree CRF for parsing. It was a submission to the PARSEME shared task 1.1 on MWE identification (Ramisch et al., 2020) and their approach is exactly the one described above with two losses being minimized. The only difference is that they include a parameter α to downweigh the loss of dependency parsing to get a better balance during training:

$$loss = loss_{mwe} + \alpha * loss_{dep} \quad (2)$$

α was set experimentally to either $\frac{1}{300}$ or $\frac{1}{700}$, depending on the language (the PARSEME shared task 1.1 is highly multilingual with data sets for 18 different languages). This system won the shared task which was attributed to the impact of the parsing as an auxiliary task. However, the results show that the multi-task system did not perform better across the board, but only for half the languages. In addition, if we take the mean-average over all languages, the identification-only system outperforms the multi-task one: **68.58** vs. 68.57 for Global MWE-based and **40.40** vs. 39.47 for Unseen MWE-based⁵. In other words: It is hardly justified to claim that the parsing helped the identification process in this case.

However, we believe the performance of the multi-task system could be improved by dynamically weighing the losses instead of using experimental parameters. In other words: Maybe they just did not find the optimal values. This is why we equipped their system, MTLB-STRUCT, with a dynamic weighing mechanism. We will go into more detail about this in section 4.1.

Furthermore, we employed an approach based on contrastive learning in the same vein as Yavas et al. (2025) by “enhancing” a standard BERT model with parsing information. More on that in Chapter 4.2.

2 Related Work on Fine-tuning Embeddings with Contrastive Learning

Yavas et al. (2025) are concerned with the issue that the embeddings of pre-trained language models often do not align well with word senses and because of that underperform in word similarity tasks. Semantically enriching the embedding space by fine-tuning the model is one way to alleviate this issue. However, fine-tuning can negatively influence the topology of word embeddings, e.g. the isotropy. This in turn is known to reduce their expressiveness. Therefore, Yavas et al. (2025) examine two different fine-tuning methods and their effect on the topology of embeddings: *Supervised Contrastive Learning (SCL)* and *Supervised Predictive Learning (SPL)*. The former’s objective is to bring instances of the same class closer together, while the latter tries to predict the correct class of an instance (which of course is the standard way of fine-tuning a model). These two methods are evaluated on the Word-in-context (WiC) task. The results show that SCL achieved more consistent improvements compared to SPL. This inspired us to use SCL to enrich our own model with syntactic information by pushing tokens closer together in the embeddings space that share dependency relations. This will be discussed in more detail in Section 4.2.

⁴We would have three losses if we not only predicted the tree but also the dependency labels.

⁵MWE-based means that a prediction is only considered a true positive if every component of a MWE is tagged. Otherwise, it does not count. Unseen means, as the name suggests, that it measures the performance on MWE types not seen during training.

3 Data

For our experiments, we used a subset of the PARSEME 1.2 corpus (Ramisch et al., 2020) and the STREUSLE⁶ corpus (Schneider et al., 2014; Schneider and Smith, 2015). The PARSEME 1.2 corpus consists of individual data sets for 18 different languages which were all annotated for VMWEs according to the same annotation guidelines (Khelil et al., 2022), except for some minor language-specific differences. Of these 18, the most suitable data set for our purposes was the French one, due to its large size (compared to the other data sets) and – more importantly – due to the fact that its accompanying UD dependency trees are exclusively gold standard. This minimizes the possibility of error propagation caused by incorrect parses when relying on parsing information.

The STREUSLE corpus consists of the review section of the English Web Treebank (Bies et al., 2012), which has been annotated for MWEs and semantic supersenses. The initial annotation of MWEs was very broad in that annotators were instructed to mark all combinations of words they believed to be MWEs, regardless of syntactic construction (Schneider et al., 2014). There was no syntactic information given in the MWE annotation. The only distinction made was between *strong* (opaque idioms) and *weak* (collocations) MWEs. However, for release 4.1, PARSEME categories for verbal MWE types were added to STREUSLE, which made it suitable for our purposes.⁷ In addition, STREUSLE’s source data is a subset of the English Web Treebank (EWT) (Bies et al., 2012), so it also contains gold dependency annotations.

VMWE Category	PARSEME FR	STREUSLE
IAV	0	121
IRV	1501	0
LVC.cause	97	12
LVC.full	1878	124
MVC	22	0
VID	2156	320
VPC.full	0	207
VPC.semi	0	98
Total	5654	882

Table 1: Distribution of VMWE categories in PARSEME FR and STREUSLE

Table 1 shows a comparison between the PARSEME FR data set and STREUSLE in terms of VMWE frequencies. One obvious difference is the number of VMWEs which is much larger for the FR data set. This is due to the simple fact that it is much larger than STREUSLE: 525,992 vs. 55,000 tokens. Also, we can see that some VMWE types do not occur in some data sets while in others, they do. For example, VPCs do occur in STREUSLE but not in PARSEME FR. This is to be expected since VPCs are rare in Romance languages, but very common in Germanic ones. However, the non-occurrence of IAVs in PARSEME FR has another reason: PARSEME introduced IAVs as an experimental and optional category (and they have this status to this day), thus most annotators chose not to annotate them even if they could have.

One important difference between the STREUSLE and PARSEME annotation schemes is how they handle overlap, that is, cases where a token belongs to multiple MWEs. PARSEME allows for a token to have multiple labels, while a token in STREUSLE can only belong to one group. Hence, the annotation process is not identical but still close enough for our purposes.

One obvious question that should be addressed is why we did not use the English PARSEME data set, since both, FR and EN, were annotated (in theory) according to identical annotation guidelines. The reason for this is the poor quality of the English PARSEME data set. Even after a revision for the PARSEME 1.3 corpus (Savary et al., 2023), a quick manual inspection shows that it contains a lot of noise with many invalid sentences like *THAI FOOD AND ASIAN, Davis* or *- ENRON.XLS « File: ENRON.XLS »*⁸.

4 Experiments

4.1 Multi-task

Multi-task learning can be challenging if each task’s loss has a different scale and this seems to be the case for dependency parsing and MWE identification. It can be observed during training that the former is usually much higher

⁶Supersense-Tagged Repository of English with a Unified Semantics for Lexical Expressions

⁷<https://github.com/nert-nlp/streusle> [Accessed: 05/28/2025]

⁸These are actual example “sentences” from the English PARSEME data set.

than the latter. To counter different scales we can try to find weights for individual losses in order to balance them out. However, finding the right values manually can be difficult as exemplified by the results of Taslimipour et al. (2020). As argued in the introduction, it cannot really be stated that they found the ideal weights, since their multi-task results were slightly worse than those of the identification-only setup. Nevertheless, we still believe that training both tasks with a shared representation can be beneficial, i.e. we assume that two weights exist that result in a superior performance of the joint approach. This is why we experimented with ways to dynamically weigh the individual losses instead of doing it manually. For this purpose, we used the joint architecture of Taslimipour et al. (2020), MTLB-STRUCT, and combined it with a dynamic weighing mechanism which is based on Kendall et al. (2018). Kendall et al. (2018) leverage the concept of aleatoric uncertainty that denotes the kind of noise in a data set that cannot be reduced by collecting more data, but is inherent to the thing observed. For example, no matter how much data we collect by rolling a dice, we will never know the outcome of the next throw.⁹ To be exact, Kendall et al. (2018) use task-dependent or *homoscedastic* uncertainty which, as the name suggests, denotes the average level of noise/randomness for specific data sets. The idea is then to downweigh tasks with high uncertainty and boost those that have low uncertainty. See Kendall et al. (2018) for the details. Before we tested this method, we extended MTLB-STRUCT with the capability to predict not only the dependency heads, but also the arc labels in order for it to perform full parsing. Consequently, we had three individual losses to find weights for:

$$loss = w_1 * loss_{mwe} + w_2 * loss_{heads} + w_3 * loss_{deps} \quad (3)$$

See Section 5.1 for the results.¹⁰

4.2 Contrastive Learning

Our second approach is based on *Supervised Contrastive Learning (SCL)* that we use analogously to Yavas et al. (2025) for syntactic dependency relations. We use a standard cross-entropy loss function but use sense-enhanced or syntax-enhanced embeddings. Due to the availability of sense-enhanced embeddings for English, we tried out this approach on English data, using the STREUSLE dataset.

See Section 5.2 for the results.¹¹

5 Results

5.1 Multi-Task Approach

We evaluate all models by calculating the span-based F1 score of their output with respect to the gold test data. As is usual for BIO tagging, a span here means any B-* tag followed by one or more I-* tags, where * stands for the type of MWE. The evaluation is lenient in that a I-* tag not following a corresponding B-* or I-* tag is counted as a B-* tag for the purposes of identifying spans.

Table 2 shows the results of our experiments with the dynamic weighing mechanism based on task-dependent uncertainty. We trained our models on the French PARSEME 1.2 data set discussed in Section 3. Every model was trained for 30 epochs with *bert-base-multilingual-cased* as the underlying BERT model. To examine the effect of the dynamic weighing on MWE identification we compared it to the setup where no weights were applied to the individual losses (*Full Parsing + MWE ident.*). We can see that the dynamic weighing actually improved the performance for MWE identification substantially: 75.99 vs. 73.60. However, this is still way worse than the identification-only approach: **78.92**. Thus, even though we can state that dynamic weighing is better than no weighing at all, the weights found by this process are still less than ideal. On the other hand, parsing was improved by MWE identification as an auxiliary task, albeit only slightly and only without weighing. Nevertheless, these results are somewhat encouraging and suggest exploring other dynamic weighting methods.

5.2 Contrastive Learning

For the experiments on the English STREUSLE data with the models enhanced by syntactic and semantic information, we used our own MWE tagger: A BERT model with a linear layer on top. The BERT model was fine-tuned during training. Due to the small size of the data set, we used 10-fold cross validation. Furthermore, we used a batch-size

⁹That is where the name comes from: *alea* = ‘dice’.

¹⁰The code is available here: <https://gitlab.com/mwesempre/mtlb-depmwe-full>

¹¹The code is available here: https://github.com/rafehr/mwe_tagger

Setup	UAS	LAS	MWE-based
MWE ident. only	–	–	78.92
Full Parsing only	94.09	86.56	–
Full Parsing + MWE ident.	94.11	86.84	73.60
Full Parsing + MWE ident. + Dyn. Weighing	93.96	86.51	75.99

Table 2: Performance for the French PARSEME 1.2 data for different setups.

Model	μ_{F1}	σ_{F1}	μ_P	σ_P	μ_R	σ_R
Baseline	85.91	6.21	86.30	6.00	85.60	6.93
Sense	83.68	8.70	85.03	8.07	82.49	9.73
Syntax 0.1	59.68	41.51	60.16	41.80	59.23	41.25
Syntax 0.5	68.47	25.64	68.56	25.77	68.47	25.69
Syntax 1.0	46.59	40.50	46.12	40.04	47.10	41.04

Table 3: Mean (μ) and standard deviation (σ) of F1 score, precision (P), and recall (R) for each model

of 4 and early stopping was applied if the loss did not improve for two epochs. As a baseline model we employed *bert_base_uncased* (Devlin et al., 2019).

Table 3 shows the results where μ is the mean-average and σ is the standard deviation over 10 folds. The name of the syntax-enhanced models corresponds to the temperature they were trained with (e.g. Syntax 0.5 was trained with a temperature of 0.5). We see right away that none of our “enhanced” models performs better than the baseline (F1-score: 85.91). The sense-enhanced is closest with a F1-score of 83.68. The syntax-enhanced models are all way behind. The strongest – if you want to call it that – is Syntax 0.5 (F1-score: 68.47), followed by Syntax 0.1 (F1-score: 59.68) and Syntax 1.0 (F1-score: 46.59). For all these models, the standard deviation is very large, ranging from 25.64 to 41.51. The reason for this is that for all of these models some of the folds have an F1-score of 0.0. This is because for these folds, the model predicted the most frequent label O for all tokens, thus not predicting any MWEs at all. In any case, it is obvious that the syntax enhancement did not have the desired effect but made performance much worse. Our original idea was to build an ensemble system, combining the sense-enhanced and syntax-enhanced model where the two models were supposed to compensate for each other’s weaknesses. The bad performance of the syntax-enhanced model rendered this approach useless.

However, we tried another way to incorporate syntactic information into the sense-enhanced model: By concatenating a randomly initialized embedding (of size 64) to the BERT representation of a token that was supposed to represent the dependency relation to its head. The final classifier is then trained jointly to predict both the MWE tag and the dependency relation. Table 4 shows the (first) results.

We combined the baseline as well as the sense-enhance model with dependency relation embeddings and both performed better than the original baseline with the sense-enhanced model showing the best results with an F1-score of 87.88. We assumed this was because the sense-enhanced model might have learned something about semantics the original BERT did not know even though it lost some valuable information about syntax in the process which was then incorporated back again with help of the dependency relation embeddings. However, this proved to be wrong when we ran the experiments again and failed to replicate the results. For every run we got very different results, thus we performed 10 times 10-fold cross validation to obtain the most accurate results possible.

Table 5 displays the mean-average over 100 folds for the F1-scores. Disappointingly, the baseline still performs best which proves that we did not gain any advantage by combining BERT embeddings with dependency relation embeddings. Note that for some folds, the model predicted the most frequent label, O, for all tokens, resulting in a recall of 0. Our last straw was to investigate whether the performance for some VMWE types was boosted. The reason for this is that most VMWE types are syntactically defined, e.g. a VPC is a combination of a verb and a particle and a LVC is a combination of a verb with an object. VIDs, in contrast, have no such restriction in their definition. Our theory

Model	μ_{F1}	σ_{F1}	μ_P	σ_P	μ_R	σ_R
Baseline + dep. embs	86.80	6.38	87.32	6.78	86.39	6.79
Sense + dep. embs	87.88	4.49	88.36	4.32	87.47	5.29

Table 4: Mean (μ) and standard deviation (σ) of F1 score, precision (P), and recall (R) for each model coupled with dependency relation embeddings

Model	μ_{F1}
Baseline	86.29
Baseline + dep. embs	85.46
Sense	84.86
Sense + dep. embs	85.54

Table 5: Mean (μ) after 10-fold cross validation $\times 10$

was that the dependency relation embeddings might help with all VMWEs types except VIDs, but this also does not seem to be the case. The performance got worse across the board for every VMWE type.

6 Conclusion and Future Work

In this paper, we investigated the relationship between dependency parsing and verbal multiword expression (VMWE) identification, revisiting the widely held assumption that the two tasks can mutually benefit from one another. Across a range of joint and syntax-enhanced modeling approaches — including multi-task learning, uncertainty-based dynamic loss weighting, supervised contrastive learning over dependency relations, and dependency relation embeddings — we found that none consistently outperformed a strong MWE-only baseline. Dynamic loss weighting proved to be the most promising multi-task variant, yet still fell short of the task-specific model. Contrastive learning with syntactic supervision led to severe performance degradation and unstable training, with several cross-validation folds collapsing to the majority-class prediction. Dependency relation embeddings showed initial promise but failed to replicate across repeated experiments, suggesting that the gains were due to random variation rather than a genuine learning signal.

Taken together, our results paint a sobering picture: despite strong theoretical motivation and the syntactically-defined nature of many VMWE categories, current neural models based on pretrained language representations do not appear to benefit from explicit syntactic supervision for VMWE identification. One plausible explanation is that models like BERT already implicitly encode a great deal of syntactic information, leaving little room for explicit syntactic signals to add value. Another possibility is that the interface between syntactic and MWE-specific representations needs to be designed more carefully than the approaches explored here allow.

Future work could explore several promising directions. First, it would be worthwhile to investigate whether more expressive graph-based or structured prediction models, rather than sequence labelers, can better integrate syntactic structure. Second, probing the extent to which pretrained language models already capture the syntactic cues relevant to VMWE identification could clarify when and why explicit syntax fails to help. Third, expanding experiments to additional languages in the PARSEME dataset — particularly those with richer morphosyntax or higher rates of discontinuous VMWEs — may reveal settings where syntactic information plays a more decisive role. Finally, exploring cross-lingual transfer scenarios, where syntactic supervision could serve as a language-agnostic bridge, represents another avenue worth pursuing.

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